

Sesbania green manure, yield in dry matter (grain or straw) increased over control (see table). Application of mineral nitrogen was significantly less effective. Nitrogen content of grain and straw was significantly higher in green-manured plots than in plots without

green manure.

If extrapolation of the data to the field is valid, we can conclude that the use of *S. rostrata* as green manure permits yields as high as 6 t/ha in a soil with lower than average fertility, such as the one used in this experiment. ■

Effect of *Sesbania rostrata* green manure on the yield and nitrogen content of rice.

Treatment ^b	Av dry yield (g/m ²)		Nitrogen content (%)		Av nitrogen yield (g N/m ²) in grain + straw
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
PK + green manure	596 a	772 a	1.80a	0.94 a	18.17a
PK + N (60 kg/ha)	381 b	484 b	1.27 b	0.49 b	7.21 b
PK (control)	212 c	276 c	1.14 b	0.58 b	4.02 c

^aFigures followed by same letter do not significantly differ at 1% level. ^bSix microplots per treatment.

Rice crop productivity in alkali soil reclaimed by gypsum or pyrites — a case of eastern Uttar Pradesh

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Alkaline soils constitute a permanent constraint to rice production in eastern Uttar Pradesh. A series of experiments were initiated in alkali soil (pH 10.4) during the 1976 rainy season and

repeated in 1977 and 1978. Plots measured 5 × 4 in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Gypsum was applied at 0, 3, 6, 9, and 12 t/ha. Pyrites were applied at 0, 1.5, 3, 4.5 and 6 t/ha. Pyrites applied were half that of gypsum because the sulfur content (30%) of pyrites is double that of gypsum. In addition, the cost of one ton of pyrites is almost double that of gypsum. Rice husk and sawdust at a maximum dose of 7.5 t/ha also were used.

Medium duration variety IR24 was

grown during the first year and Jaya was grown during the second and third years. Transplanting of 5- to 6-week-old seedlings in early to mid-July was at 15-cm plant spacing with 4 to 5 seedlings/hill. Fertilizer was applied at 120 kg N, 50-60 kg P₂O₅, and 32-40 kg K₂O/ha. Zinc sulfate was applied at 35 to 40 kg/ha.

Rice husk and sawdust had no effect. Grain yield dramatically increased with increasing doses of gypsum and pyrites (see table). Yield increased from a minimum of 1.0 t/ha in original alkali soil to a maximum of 6.0 t/ha in pyrite-treated and 6.8 t/ha in gypsum-treated plots. Gypsum consistently proved superior to pyrites in enhancing rice yields from alkali soil. Yields in nontreated original alkali soil plots also went up from 1.0 t/ha to 2.0 t/ha suggesting some spontaneous improvement in soil even without any chemical amendments. This might be possible because continued application of fertilizers and zinc sulfate and proper water management aided natural leaching of salts. Yield levels after chemical amelioration suggest that alkali soils are inherently productive and that good rice yields can be obtained with proper soil-water-crop management practices. ■

Effect of gypsum and pyrites on rice yield from alkali soils of Kumarganj (Faizabad), India.

Application rates ^a (t/ha)		Yield (t/ha)								
Gypsum	Pyrites	1976			1977			1978		
		Gypsum	Pyrites	Difference	Gypsum	Pyrites	Difference	Gypsum	Pyrites	Difference
0	0	1.0	1.1	-0.1	1.6	1.6	0	2.0	2.0	0
3	1.5	1.9	1.7	0.2	2.9	2.8	0.1	3.4	3.1	0.3
6	3.0	3.5	2.7	0.8	4.6	4.0	0.6	4.7	4.3	0.4
9	4.5	4.8	4.2	0.6	6.0	5.2	0.8	6.2	5.6	0.6
12		5.3	4.6	0.7	6.4	5.9	0.5	6.8	6.0	0.8
LSD (0.05)		0.4	0.4		0.4	0.3		0.3	0.3	

^aThe soil amendments were applied only once, in 1976.

Influence of presowing soil water and seed iron-coating on iron in soil and yield of dryland rice

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An experiment on a calcareous Vertisol (pH 8.7, organic carbon 0.61%, Olsen-P 8.74 ppm, DTPA extractable Fe 1.38 ppm, Mn 2.64 ppm, and CaCO₃ equi-

valent 8.2%) at Rahuri during the 1980 rainy season examined the influence of water treatment (control and one irrigation daily to about soil saturation) 15 days before sowing and seed coating with an iron compound (control and 2% Fe coating through FeSO₄·7H₂O and Fe EDTA) on the availability of soil Fe and yield of dryland rice cultivar Karjat 184. Field moisture capacity of 27-35% was maintained from sowing to maturity.

Soil saturation before sowing signifi-

cantly increased DTPA extractable Fe at 15 days and at sowing, tillering, panicle initiation, and flowering stages of rice growth (see table). This could have been caused by the moderately reduced soil conditions that resulted from soil saturation 15 days before sowing (Eh reduced from + 502 to + 390 mV and pH from 8.70 to 8.15). Coating seed with Fe compounds had no influence on the release of Fe in the soil.

Grain and straw yields were signifi-

Rice yield and release of iron in soil as influenced by presowing soil water treatments and coating seed with iron compounds at Rahuri, India.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)		Release of iron in soil (ppm)						
	Grain	Straw	Water treatment before sowing		Sowing	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Harvest
			1 day	15 days					
Water treatment									
Control	2.1	2.4	1.64	1.64	2.64	2.91	2.88	2.60	1.71
Soil saturation	2.3	2.7	1.72	3.73	3.77	3.16	3.06	3.08	1.98
Seed coating									
Control	2.1	2.4	—	—	3.18	3.06	2.96	2.79	1.84
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	2.2	2.6	—	—	3.20	2.97	2.85	2.85	1.97
Fe EDTA	2.2	2.6	—	—	3.24	3.01	2.98	2.89	1.71
Water treatment									
F-test	**	**	ns	**	**	**	**	**	ns
S.E. ±	0.21	0.17	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.09
C.D. at 5%	0.63	0.51	—	0.12	0.14	0.07	0.07	0.15	—
Seed coating									
F-test	**	**	—	—	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
S.E. ±	0.25	0.21	—	—	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.12
C.D. at 5%	0.75	0.63	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Interaction									
F-test	**	**	—	—	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

cantly higher under the presowing soil saturation treatment. This might be due to the increased availability of Fe.

Coating seed with FeSO₄·7H₂O and

Fe EDTA significantly increased yield, probably because of the increased availability of Fe to rice plants. The interaction between presowing soil water

treatment and coating seed with Fe compounds significantly increased yield. ■

Urea application and time of incorporation in Bangladesh paddy

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Urea fertilizer usually is incorporated into paddy soil soon after application. But urea is not well absorbed by soil particles in ill-drained paddy fields with deep standing water. A large portion remains in the standing water, even after intensive incorporation practices. The unincorporated urea may be lost through volatilization and denitrification. Because ammonium is easily absorbed by soil particles, incorporation a few days after urea application, after a major portion has been ammonified, may increase the effect of the fertilizer.

A first trial on soil incubation showed that the highest amount of exchangeable ammonium remained in the soil with incorporation 2 to 4 days after urea application (Table 1). In a field trial using 253-m² plots in 1981 T. aman season, incorporation 4 days after application maximized paddy yields (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Effect of incorporation lag on recovery of urea^a nitrogen after 17-day incubation in Bangladesh.

Incorporation (days after application)	Oxidative layer (mm)	Ammonium nitrogen (ppm)
0	6.8	74
2	6.6	103
4	6.5	102
6	6.0	93
9	5.2	76
No incorporation	9.8	70

^aRate of 40 kg N/ha, 5 cm standing water, extracted soil layer 5 cm.

Table 2. Effect of time of soil incorporation of applied urea on paddy yield in Bangladesh.^a

Incorporation (days after application)	Paddy yield (t/ha)
0	5.0
1	5.0
2	5.3
3	6.7
4	6.6
5	6.5

^aBR 10 variety, 3-split application (40-20-20 kg N/ha).

Effect of insecticide application on nitrogen transformation in flooded soil

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A soil incubation experiment studied the effects of soil-applied insecticides such as lindane, carbofuran, FMC 35001, and the herbicide butachlor on nitrogen (N) transformations in flooded fields at Coimbatore. The soil was a moderately drained, deep clay loam with a pH of 7.5 and low available N. Pesticides were applied at field dosage. The soil was

kept flooded. NH₄-N, NO₃-N, and NO₂-N were determined at different stages of incubation. A completely randomized block design was replicated four times.

Application of lindane and butachlor resulted in lower levels of nitrites and nitrates 2 days after application (see table). Later, the reduction was not significant. A higher accumulation of NH₄-N appeared at early stages but later the NH₄-N was nitrified into NO₂ and NO₃.

Lindane and butachlor seem to be slightly inhibitory to some nitrifying microorganisms, slowing down the nitrification reaction for about 2 days. This effect slowly disappeared and was not felt after 5 days. ■